

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-74-IC-1% 05 rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	32	Acq. Method Set:	1% 210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 74
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	2/18/2023 9:34:16 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 16:26:31 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.285	3646446	41.13	174971
2	11.260	797536	9.00	36636
3	11.712	780473	8.80	36933
4	12.636	3640556	41.07	148338

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-62-IC-1% 05 asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20230306
Vial:	33	Acq. Method Set:	1% 210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 62
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/6/2023 19:27:38 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 16:22:57 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.047	2902	0.17	151
2	12.188	27473	1.62	910
3	12.957	426	0.03	52
4	13.988	1669332	98.19	46474